

A

Monoassociated Infection

B

Competition Infection

Supplementary Figure S8. Infant mouse colonization assays of WT and $\Delta pflA$ in the large intestine after 20h. (A) Monoassociated infections of 3-5 day old infant mice reported as CFU/g intestine. (B) Competition infections of 3-5 day old infant mice reported as a competitive index score calculated as a ratio of output versus input $[(\text{Target}_{\text{Output}}/\Delta\text{lacZ}_{\text{Output}}) / (\text{Target}_{\text{Input}}/\Delta\text{lacZ}_{\text{Input}})]$. WT and $\Delta pflA$ strains were co-inoculated with a *pflA*+ ΔlacZ strain to determine the relative fitness of each test strain. Data for each experiment was obtained from 4-5 independent mouse colonization infections for WT and 7-8 mouse infections for $\Delta pflA$. The bar represents geometric mean. Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad PRISM where significance was tested on log transformed data by Student's t-test; * indicates $p < 0.05$.